

SOLVING THE MULTIDIMENSIONAL KNAPSACK PROBLEM USING A GENETIC ALGORITHM

VLADIMIR JANKOVIĆ¹

¹ University of Belgrade, Faculty of Mathematics, vladimir.jan.98@gmail.com, 0009-0008-1667-9966

Abstract: *The Multidimensional Knapsack Problem (MdKP) is a generalization of the classic knapsack problem, aiming to maximize profit under capacity constraints for each dimension $d \in \mathbb{N}$. A linear integer mathematical formulation of the problem is presented and utilized within the exact solver CPLEX 22.1.1 to obtain optimal solutions. To find high-quality solutions for larger instances, a heuristic based on the concept of the Genetic Algorithm (GA) was implemented. Parts of the proposed GA were parallelized to enhance the algorithm's performance. For testing purposes, existing instances from the well-known OR-Library were used, along with newly generated small, medium, and large problem instances. The proposed genetic algorithm was run on all considered instances, and the obtained results were analyzed and compared with the optimal or best-known solutions. Experimental results show that the solutions obtained by the genetic algorithm match all optimal solutions found by CPLEX 22.1.1 for small instances. For medium-sized instances, the GA reaches most of the optimal solutions or yields near-optimal ones. For large instances that CPLEX 22.1.1 was unable to solve, the proposed GA provides solutions within a short execution time.*

Keywords: *Multidimensional knapsack problem, mathematical programming, heuristic, genetic algorithm.*